

Synthesis of some New 2-(4-Tolyl)-3-(aroyl/4-aminobenzoyl/4-arylideneaminobenzoyl)-4-oxo-4H-2,3-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazines as Possible Anticonvulsants

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A number of 2-(4-tolyl)-3-(aroyl/4-aminobenzoyl/4-arylideneaminobenzoyl)-4-oxo-4H-2,3-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazines were synthesised and tested for their anticonvulsant activity. These compounds were, however, found to be inactive against pentylenetetrazole-induced convulsions in mice at a dose of 80 mg/kg.

1,3-Benzoxazines have been reported to exhibit diverse biological activities such as sedative¹, hypnotic², and analgesic^{3,4}. Furthermore, Agarwal *et al.*⁵ have observed interesting anticonvulsant activity among several benzylidene derivatives. In view of these observations, it is of much interest to synthesise the title benzoxazines as per Scheme 1.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded using KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The pmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a Varian A60D instrument using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of all the compounds was checked on silica gel G plates using iodine vapours as visualising agent.

Scheme 1

2-(4-Tolyl)-4-oxo-4H-2,3-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazine (1): A mixture of salicylamide (0.03 mol), *p*-tolualdehyde (0.03 mol) with catalytic amount of concentrated H₂SO₄ (2 drops) was refluxed in anhydrous benzene (75 ml) for 12 h in a flask fitted with Dean-Stark arrangement. The excess benzene was distilled off under reduced pressure. The solid residue so obtained was washed successively with 5% sodium hydroxide, 5% sodium bisulphite solutions and water. It was dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (78%), m.p. 162° (lit.⁶ 168°); ν_{max} 1 600 (Ph), 1 680 (C=O), 2 900 (CH str.) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH str.).

2-(4-Tolyl)-3-aroyl-4-oxo-4H-2,3-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazines (2a-f): A mixture of the benzoxazine (1; 0.002 mol), substituted-benzoyl chloride (0.002 mol), triethylamine (0.03 mol) and anhydrous benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 5-6 h. Triethylamine hydrochloride thus separated out on cooling was filtered off. The filtrate was shaken successively with sodium bicarbonate solution and water. It was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Benzene was distilled off under reduced pressure to afford a solid which was crystallised from ethanol. The compounds were characterised by their sharp m.ps., elemental analysis and by the disappearance of the band for NH and appearance of a band at 1 780 cm⁻¹ for imido carbonyl in its ir spectra (Table 1).

2-(4-Tolyl)-3-(4-amino)benzoyl-4-oxo-4H-2,3-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazine (3): 2d (0.003 mol) was

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF 2-(4-TOLYL)-3-ARYL-4-OXO-4H-2,3-DIHYDRO-1,3-BENZOXAZINES* (2a-f)

Sl no	R	M p °C	Mol formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			ALD ₅₀ mg/kg
				C	H	N	
2a	H	95	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ NO ₂	76.45 (76.96)	4.48 (4.95)	3.71 (4.08)	681
2b	4-Methoxy	170	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ NO ₂	73.37 (73.99)	4.62 (5.09)	3.41 (3.75)	825
2c	4-Chloro	118	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ NO ₂ Cl	69.32 (69.93)	3.87 (4.23)	3.38 (3.70)	>1000
2d**	4-Nitro	180	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅	67.53 (68.04)	3.86 (4.12)	6.85 (7.21)	825
2e	2-Chloro	90	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ NO ₂ Cl	67.28 (69.93)	3.94 (4.23)	3.43 (3.70)	>1000
2f	2-Nitro	116	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅	67.49 (68.04)	3.75 (4.12)	6.82 (7.21)	>1000

*ν_{max} 1 600 (Ph), 1 700 (CO of benzoxazine), 1 780 (CO of imide side chain), 2 950–2 960 cm⁻¹ (CH str.)
 **δ(CDCl₂) 2 15 (3H, s, CH₃), 6 90 (1H, s, CH at C₂), 7 10–7 80 (10H, m, Ar) and 8 15 (2H, m, Ar)

dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) and Raney-Ni (0.5 g) was added to it. Hydrazine hydrate (99%) was then carefully added at room temperature and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 3–5 h. The resulting solution was filtered. Ethanol was distilled off from the filtrate under reduced pressure. The solid residue so obtained was crystallised from ethyl acetate (64%), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 73.27; H, 4.83; N, 7.51. C₂₂H₁₆N₂O₅ requires: C, 73.74; H, 5.02; N, 7.82%). The compound was further characterised by disappearance of IR bands for NO₂ (1 360 and 1 550 cm⁻¹) and appearance of bands for NH₂ (3 300–3 400 cm⁻¹).

2-(4-Tolyl)-3-(4-arylideneamino)benzoyl-4-oxo-4H-2,3-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazines (4a-c): A mixture of 3 (0.002 mol), an araldehyde (0.002 mol), ethanol (20 ml) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a steam-bath for 5–6 h. Excess ethanol was removed by distillation. The solid mass thus obtained was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

ALD₅₀ and gross behavioural effects: ALD₅₀ was determined following the method of Horn⁷. During these studies using high doses of the compounds in groups of 4 mice each, animals were simultaneously observed for gross behavioural effects as well. One-fifth of ALD₅₀ dose was administered i.p. in groups of 5 mice each and the animals were observed continuously for 1 h and later on at intervals of 0.5 h upto 5 h for any effect on gross behaviour. Signs of stimulation were manifested by increased SMA (spontaneous motor activity), piloerection, exopthalmos, clonic and tonic convulsions. Similarly, signs of depression were recorded as decreased SMA, hypothermia, crouching, reduced muscle tone, loss of righting, corneal and pinnal reflexes etc.

Anticonvulsant activity: It was determined by the method of Swinyard *et al.*⁸. Compounds were found without any toxic manifestations as shown

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF 2-(4-TOLYL)-3-(4-ARYLIDENEAMINO)-BENZOYL-4-OXO-4H-2,3-DIHYDRO-1,3-BENZOXAZINES* (4a-c)

Sl. no.	R	M. p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			ALD ₅₀ mg/kg
				C	H	N	
4a	Phenyl	176	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	77.48 (78.02)	4.56 (4.93)	6.13 (6.27)	>1000
4b	4-Methoxyphenyl	189	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂	75.32 (75.63)	4.78 (5.04)	5.62 (5.88)	>1000
4c	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	203	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₂	73.13 (73.51)	4.75 (5.13)	5.12 (5.53)	>1000

*ν_{max} 1 600 (Ph), 1 640–1 660 (N-CH str.), 1 700 (CO of benzoxazine), 1 780 (CO of imide side chain), 2 950 cm⁻¹ (CH str.)

Bio-assay: All the compounds were screened for their toxicity, gross behaviour and anticonvulsant activity against pentylenetetrazole-induced convulsions in mice.

by their ALD₅₀ values. The compounds showed no significant change in their gross behaviour and were also found to be inactive against pentylenetetrazole-induced convulsions in mice.

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